

The Prehistoric Potential of the Southern Batinah Region

A First Survey Campaign

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1. Introduction

As part of the Italian-Omani Archaeological Mission at Al-Tikha (Rustaq, Oman) directed by Dr. Khaled Douglas from Sultan Qaboos University and Prof. Sara Pizzimenti from University of Pisa (Economou *et al.* 2022), we began an archaeological survey in order to deepen our understanding of the prehistoric potential of the Southern Batinah Region. The archaeological survey has been directed by Dr. Niccolò Mazzucco (University of Pisa), together with Dr. Giulia Ricci (CNRS-Lampea), Giada Pirrone and Simone Sani (University of Pisa). The campaign has been carried out between the 24th of January and the 3rd of February 2023. The main goal of this campaign was to survey a wide transect between the coastal and mountain areas, focusing on two main types of evidence: possible shell-middens in the coastal fringe of the Al Batinah South region and open-air sites/lithic scatters on fluvial terraces in the Central Hajar Mountains, especially seeking for Neolithic and pre-Neolithic chronologies.

The Rustaq-Batinah area has been previously object of an extensive archaeological survey (RBAS) by the Durham University and the Sultan Qaboos University, directed by Dr. Derek Kennet and Dr. Nasser al-Jahwari (Kennet *et al.* 2015; Deadman *et al.* 2022). Although most of the survey results are still unpublished, the RBAS identified only a few prehistoric sites and lithic scatters (Bretzke *et al.* 2018), pointing out for a low visibility and/or a scarceness of Palaeolithic and Neolithic occupations in the region, especially in comparison with other regions of the Sultanate (Cleuziou & Tosi 2020).

2. Methodology

The first, preparative, phase of the survey has been made by screening satellite imagery (Esri Satellite and Bing Virtual Earth on QGIS) in order to select potential areas to be surveyed, both for what concerns fluvial terraces and dune areas left from urbanization. Further adjustments of the zones to be surveyed were made on the basis of on-field observations. Given the low number of participants to the survey campaign and the huge extent of the territory, we decided to limit our survey to small territories, moving rapidly with a vehicle from one area to another (Figures 1-3). Selected areas have been systematically surveyed on foot in closely spaced search-lines, recording the tracks using the Geopaparazzi App (Paperini *et al.* 2022) (Figure 4). Points of interest were also recorded using a specific form embedded into the application. The presence of both raw-materials (i.e. chert, radiolarite, quartz, etc.) and archaeological stone artefacts have been recorded. Samples of pottery have been collected only from surveyed sites and from stratified deposits. Area- and site-specific strategies have been also adopted in locus of particular interest: test transects have been defined in areas with relevant densities of finds and surface sediments brushed and sieved; stratigraphic pits have been realized, when necessary, to verify the integrity and the potential of the archaeological deposit. Archaeological materials have been analysed following a chaine opératoire approach, aiming to reconstruct, whenever possible, the main lithic reduction sequences for each assemblage, the knapping techniques employed and to identify the main tool types and their chronological and cultural attribution. Photos of the materials have been taken with a Nikon camera and a DNT Digital Microscope (5MP).

The main goal of our survey has been to attribute a preliminary Prehistoric Potential index (PP) (from low to high) on the basis of two main fundamental observations: the presence of flaked stone tool materials and the local availability of primary or secondary raw-materials sources in the surveyed area. This will help to design with more precision future surveys campaigns and other research activities in the area.

3. Results

As result, 23 areas have been surveyed, recording 103 points of interest (Figures 1-3). Average surveyed areas are of about 300 km², with a minimum of *ca.* 5 km² and a maximum of *ca.* 2.000 km² (Table 1). The two main type of surveyed zones are 1) remnant of the sandy dune environment still accessible among the modern urban fabric and 2) fluvial terraces, mainly privileging areas with heavily weathered (desert varnish) deposits, which supposedly reflect a longer period of exposure to atmospheric agents. The alluvial fan area has been mostly avoided, for both a matter of time and for being supposedly composed of more recent sediments.

Figure 1. Points of interest (N=103) recorded during the survey (Bing Virtual Earth, QGIS v. 3.26.3).

Figure 2. Areas surveyed in the coastal fringe of the Al Batinah South region (A) (Bing Virtual Earth, QGIS v. 3.26.3).

Figure 3. Areas surveyed in the foothill and mountains areas of the Central Hajar Mountains (B) (Bing Virtual Earth, QGIS v. 3.26.3).

Figure 4. Example of a surveyed area (Area 20) in the foothills of the Central Hajar Mountains. Tracks of each participant are indicated (NM, SS, GR, GP) (Bing Virtual Earth, QGIS v. 3.26.3).

Figure 5. Example of a cluster of shell middens of historic period from a satellite image (Bing Virtual Earth, QGIS v. 3.26.3).

Area	Type	Main Evidence	Main Surface Materials	Surface (km ²)	Prehistoric
Area 1	Urbanized Dunes Area	Historic	Abundant pottery sherds, Shells	37.87	low
Area 2	Active Coastal Dunes	Historic	Abundant pottery sherds, Shells, Obsidian	28.14	low
Area 3	Primary Fluvial Terrace	Historic	Few flaked cherts and quartz, Chert raw-materials	289.58	moderate
Area 4	Primary Fluvial Terrace	Historic	Few pottery sherds	884.41	low
Area 5	Primary Fluvial Terrace	Historic	Few pottery sherds	144.43	low
Area 6	Primary Fluvial Terrace	Protohistoric	No surface materials	111.49	low
Area 7	Primary Fluvial Terrace	Unknown	Few pottery sherds, Few chert raw-materials	23.82	low
Area 8	Urbanized Dunes Area	Historic	Abundant pottery sherds, Shells	649.90	low
Area 9	Urbanized Dunes Area	Historic	Abundant pottery sherds, Shells	104.00	low
Area 10	Active Coastal Dunes	Historic	Abundant pottery sherds, Shells	472.35	low
Area 11	Series of Fluvial Terraces	Prehistoric	Abundant flaked cherts, Chert raw-materials	610.12	high
Area 12	Urbanized Dunes Area	Unknown	Shells	17.23	low
Area 13	Urbanized Dunes Area	Historic	Abundant pottery sherds, Shells, Few flaked cherts	5.00	low
Area 14	Primary Fluvial Terrace	Prehistoric	Few flaked cherts, Chert raw-materials	373.95	moderate
Area 15	Set of Fluvial Terraces	Protohistoric	No surface materials	423.10	low
Area 16	Primary Fluvial Terrace	Unknown	Quartz raw-materials	34.97	low
Area 17	Primary Fluvial Terrace	Prehistoric	Moderate flaked cherts and quartz, Quartz raw-materials	131.37	high
Area 18	Primary Fluvial Terrace	Unknown	Quartz raw-materials	13.49	low
Area 19	Primary Fluvial Terrace	Unknown	Quartz raw-materials	38.57	low
Area 20	Primary Fluvial Terrace	Protohistoric	Few flaked cherts, Chert raw-materials, Few pottery sherds	397.17	moderate
Area 21	Primary Fluvial Terrace	Prehistoric	Few flaked cherts, Chert and quartz raw-materials	1,956.65	moderate
Area 22	Primary Fluvial Terrace	Prehistoric	Moderate flaked cherts	234.11	moderate
Area 23	Active Coastal Dunes	Unknown	Shells	19.63	low

Table 1. List of areas surveyed and their main features

Figure 6. Example of shell-middens recorded during the survey. A) SH No. 3011; B) Section of the shell layer at SH 3011; C) SH No. 3018 D) SH No. 1027.

3.1. The coastal fringe

The coastal fringe is highly urbanized, especially near the current coastline, and densely cultivated in its lower part. Therefore, few remnants areas are nowadays accessible. In order not to overlap with the work done by Kennet *et al.* 2015, we avoided modern cemetery areas that have been already extensively surveyed during the RBSA project (Dr. D. Kennet, personal communication).

Some possible shell middens were already identified by screening satellite images. They appear as bright/white roundish spots of various diameters (Figure 5). Other accumulations were identified directly through on foot survey. A total of 20 shell middens have been recorded (Tab. 2). Most of them are of small dimensions, with a maximum diameter between a minimum of *ca.* 1.5 m to a maximum of *ca.* 55 m (Figure 6). On the basis of a preliminary taxonomic identification (by Dr. Kevin Lidour) of the shell species from sampled individuals, most accumulations are composed of *Mactra cf. rochebrunei* in association with a few specimens of *Conomurex persicus* *vr. beluchiensis* both edible species still nowadays collected for food by Oman costal communities. Only one shell midden, the largest (No. 1027), is composed almost completely of *Ostrea* sp., although with a minor component of *Mactra* sp. and *Terebralia* sp. (that we rarely found elsewhere). Shell middens are also systematically associated with pottery sherds, most often of Islamic period (Figure 7). This points out for a relatively recent formation of these accumulations. Three of them were tested stratigraphically, revealing the presence of only a superficial layer of shells (Figure 6, B), while no further shell layers have been detected underneath, suggesting that they mostly respond to brief episodes of molluscs consumption and accumulation. None of them provided possible prehistoric finds/layers, except for one lithic from a possible shell midden (No. 1028) (Tab. 2) in which a debris on a yellowish fine-grained chert was found .

Figure 7. Examples of pottery sherds on the surface of shell middens. A) SH No. 2001; B) SH No. 4025; C) SH No. 3011; D) SH No. 4010; E) SH No. 4014; F) SH No. 4012.

Point	Area	Preservation State	Main Species	Main Associated Materials	Max Diameter (meters)	Satellite Visibility
3011	Area 10	Good	Bivalves, Sea Gasteropods	Islamic Pottery	6,90	Yes
3012	Area 10	Bad	Bivalves, Sea Gasteropods	Islamic Pottery	3,8	Yes
3013	Area 10	Medium	Bivalves, Sea Gasteropods	None	2,5	Yes
3014	Area 10	Bad	Bivalves, Sea Gasteropods	None	2,4	Yes
3015	Area 10	Bad	Bivalves, Sea Gasteropods	None	5,5	Yes
3016	Area 10	Bad	Bivalves, Sea Gasteropods	None	4,3	Yes
3017	Area 10	Bad	Bivalves, Sea Gasteropods	None	6,8	Yes
3018	Area 10	Good	Bivalves, Sea Gasteropods	Islamic Pottery	6,9	Yes
3019	Area 10	Medium	Bivalves, Sea Gasteropods	None	1,5	Yes
3020	Area 10	Good	Bivalves, Sea Gasteropods	None	3,4	Yes
2001	Area 2	Bad	Bivalves, Sea Gasteropods	Protohistoric Pottery, Islamic Pottery	5	Yes
4025	Area 2	Medium	Bivalves, Sea Gasteropods	Protohistoric Pottery, Islamic Pottery	7,5	Yes
1028	Area 13	Bad	Bivalves, Sea Gasteropods	Chert Debris, Islamic and Modern Pottery	6,5	No
1027	Area 12	Good	Ostrea Sp., Bivalves, Terebralia P.	None	55	Yes
2012	Area 9	Bad	Bivalves, Sea Gasteropods	None	2	No
2011	Area 9	Bad	Bivalves, Sea Gasteropods	Islamic Pottery	2,5	No
2010	Area 9	Medium	Bivalves	Islamic Pottery	2	No
4014	Area 10	Bad	Bivalves, Sea Gasteropods	Islamic Pottery	1,5	Yes
4012	Area 9	Bad	Bivalves, Sea Gasteropods	Islamic Pottery	1,5	No
4010	Area 8	Bad	Bivalves, Sea Gasteropods	Islamic Pottery	1,4	Yes

Table 2. List of shell middens recorded in the coastal fringe.

Interestingly, shell middens were found not only on the coastal fringe, but also in the inner dunes areas, among the urban fabric and along the fluvial terraces in the currently cultivated fringe (i.e. Areas 8 and 9, [Figure 2](#)). Although more detailed palaeoecological and geomorphological studies are needed to reconstruct the environmental dynamics of the area, the widespread presence of specimens of *Conomurex* sp. all across the surveyed fringe suggests that the Southern Batinah coast was characterized by active beach ridges up to 10 km from the current coastline at least until Islamic period (Reinink-Smith 2015). The scarcity of prehistoric evidence, might be imputed to the strong urbanization to which the entire zone has been subjected, or due to the impact of fluvial deposits that may have covered much of the area. Future surveys will possibly improve current knowledge.

3.2. The foothill and mountainous zone

The exploration of foothill and mountainous zone included the revision of the prehistoric evidence around the Al-Tikha site and along the Wadi Sahtan, that from the Jebel Sham Ridge flew down towards the city of Rustaq, but also aimed to extend the survey to other foothill areas of the Central Hajar Mountains, until now largely unexplored.

3.2.1. Lithic Scatters

id	Area	Chronology	Raw_Mat	Finds_Num	Finds_Type
1	Area 11	Neolithic	Flint, Quartz Arenite	413	Lithics
2	Area 11	Neolithic	Flint	35	Lithics
3	Area 17	Neolithic	Flint, Quartz	68	Lithics
4	Area 22	Pre-protolithic	Flint, Quartz Arenite	75	Lithics

Table 3. List of lithic scatters found.

3.2.1.1. Area 11

Area 11 comprises a series of fluvial terraces along the course of the Wadi Sahtan and at the confluence of Wadi Sahtan and Wadi Bani Awf. We further divided Area 11 into two sectors, separated by a rounded hill of ophiolite bedrock partially covered by alluvial (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Area 11 West (left) and East (right). The arrows indicate the areas in which materials have been found.

3.2.1.1.1. East

Area 11 East has been previously surveyed by Bretzke *et al.* 2018, identifying an assemblage with typical Neolithic bifacial tools. Three test pits were later realized, revealing the presence of one, or possibly two, archaeological layers, containing materials coherent with the surface collection.

When we visited the area, we found a relatively large lithic scatter in the central sector of the upper terrace. Therefore, we decided to collect surface materials in a transect of 60 x 80 m (Figure 9), successively, brush and sieving sediments on a square of 4 x 4 m. As results, we found 416 lithics that corresponds to a possible palimpsest of finds of wide chronology, although a huge majority probably belong to a prehistoric frequentation of the area, homogeneous with the assemblage described by Bretzke *et al.* 2018.

At a macroscopic level, we recognized seven main raw-materials: two radiolarites, two cherts, hyaline quartz, quartz, and quartz arenite. The dominant raw-material is a dark red radiolarite (56.7%), medium to fine grained, of massive appearance, with occasional black phylliform and/or rounded inclusions. Even if only at a macroscopic observation, radiolarites seem present (Figure 10, B). The second type (4,3%), is probably part of the same

Figure 9. Example of a cluster of shell middens of historic period from a satellite image (Bing Virtual Earth, QGIS v. 3.26.3).

formation, a red-orange radiolarite, with abundant iron oxides (Figure 10, C-D). The third type (6,7%) groups several yellowish/beige fine-grained cherts, characterized by black inclusions and iron oxides (Figure 10, E-F). The fourth type (4,5%) includes several varieties of a grey-greenish chert, massive, fine-grained (Figure 10, G). The fifth class is a quartz arenite (1,9%), of dark colour, medium-fine grained (Figure 10, H). Finally, we highlight the presence of both white quartz (0.5%) and hyaline quartz (1.9%). Indeterminate materials amount to 22.5%.

Considering the limited amount of material for the lithotypes from 2 to 7, we can only reconstruct the chaîne opératoire for the first class, the dark red radiolarite. This raw-material is available locally or at few distances from the Area 11. We spotted a natural outcrop of radiolarite at about 6 km as the crow flies, on a small hill east of the modern city of Rustaq (Figure 11). The presence of the same outcrops have been highlighted also in the site of Al-Tikha (Dr. K. Douglas, personal communication).

Two main technical systems have been identified. One is directed towards the obtention of flakes, laminar flakes, and microlithic quadrangular flakes. A peculiar feature is the presence of some laminar flakes with convergent edges and a dorsal ridge displaced in respect to the debitage axis; although it is not possible to state whether those flakes are products or trimming elements used to recentre the debitage surface.

Cores are mostly obtained from plaquettes, using the natural surface as striking platform in order to extract blanks from the short flanks. In lesser extent, pebbles are also used to produce polyhedral cores with series of unidirectional extractions from adjacent striking platforms. The second system consist of plaquettes and pebbles that are flaked into pyramidal-shaped cores from which bladelets are produced. Striking platforms are in both cases prepared from the debitage surface. Finally, a few items suggest that also bipolar on anvil techniques was in use. In particular, one core from a pebble shows the characteristic stigmata of this flaking system, with an acute striking angle opposed to the natural pebble surface showing marks of percussion (Vadillo Conesa *et al.* 2021). There also some secondary flakes from bipolar on anvil, also called 'quartier d'orange'. Some core trimming elements have been observed, a resharpening flakes of the striking platform, and a crested blade, confirming that the entire

Figure 10. Macroscopic photos of the main lithotypes, realized with a DNT Digital microscope. A-B) Type 1: Dark red radiolarite, with black phylliform and rounded inclusions (A) and possible radiolarians (B). C-D) Type 2: Red-orange radiolarite, probably belonging to the same formation of Type 1 with iron oxides and radiolarians. E-F) Type 3: Yellowish-beige fine grained chert with black inclusions and iron oxides. G) Type 4: grey-greenish, massive, fine-grained chert. H) Type 5: Quartz arenite.

Figure 11. Area 20. Natural outcrops of dark red radiolarite.

reduction sequence is locally represented. Used flaking techniques are direct percussion with hard hammer and tangential percussion with soft hammer, mineral or organic.

Flakes, laminar flakes and rectangular ones are intensely retouched to produce side-scrapers, end-scrapers, notches and denticulate tools (**Figure 12**). Flakes show up to four retouched sides, producing tools of quadrangular shape. Other tools are: two borers, one mesial fragment of a possible bifacial tool, and two tangs fragments with biconvex section from pressure flaked arrowheads. Our study confirms the attribution to the Neolithic period, in agreement with the radiocarbon dates obtained by Bretzke *et al.* 2018, but also provides new data on the technical systems involved in lithic production and providing additional details on the raw-material management.

3.2.1.2. Area 11 West

In the west sector of Area 11, a new lithic scatter has been identified (**Figure 13**). Materials were spread on an area of approximately 100 m². The collection is comprised of 40 items, of which 77% in radiolarite, corresponding to the Type 1 found in the East sector and coherent with the chert outcrops spotted in Area 20. The remaining are made on indeterminate raw-materials (17%) and one tool in quartz arenite (3%).

Considering the low number of specimens it is not possible to reconstruct the entire technical systems, but a few elements suggest that the assemblage is homogenous with the one collected in the East sector of the same area. For example, two multidirectional flake-cores, with preparation of the knapping platform from the debitage surface, and the same quadrangular and laminar flakes as observed in the neighbouring surveyed area.

Of special relevance, a distal fragment of a bifocal tool that further confirm the attribution of the assemblage to the Neolithic period.

3.2.1.3. Area 17

In order to understand the occupation of the inner mountainous areas, four fluvial terraces have been selected in the Ad Dakhiliyah region. Of them only one terrace, above the modern village of Al Mahda, provided archaeological finds. Materials have been found on the top of the terrace, in an cleared area, in which larger stones were removed, probably by the local community, possibly for ceremonies, feasting or other ludic activities. However, a small part of the materials were also found outside of the cleared area, suggesting that all archaeological finds were actually in situ.

After surveying of the entire sector, a transect of 20 x 2 m has been delimited in the area of greater finds concentration, superficial sediments brushed and sieved (**Figure 14**). As result, a total of 70 flaked tool have been

Figure 12. A) Example of a quadrangular flake from AREA11 with two retouched edges. B) Two tangs fragments of biconvex section from pressure flaked arrowheads (*the reconstruction of the arrowhead type/shape it is only hypothetical to help the reader visualize the tool approximate shape*).

Figure 13. Area 11 West. General view of the lithic scatter (left) and detail of a lithic tool found on the surface (right).

recovered. There is a predominance of hyaline quartz (57.1%) and quartz (8.6%), followed by the fine-grained yellowish-beige cherts (32.9%) and quartz arenite (1.4%). For what concerns the hyaline quartz and quartz assemblage, three cores were found: prismatic, unidirectional cores for the production of microflakes and bladelets. In two cases the striking platforms were prepared from the debitage surface. The main flaking technique is direct percussion, but also bipolar knapping on anvil has been highlighted, as it is shown from some of the bladelets.

Quadrangular flakes, microflakes and bladelets are retouched in a relevant proportion (24%). The most common tools are side- and end-scrapers (5), one notched tool and one tangled arrowhead with probable impact traces (Figure 15, C). It is remarkable the presence of two end-scrapers bearing traces of adhesive substances.

For what concerns the chert assemblage, we can remark the absence of cores. Blanks are mostly flakes (26%), but some laminar flakes are also present. Borers, notched tools, flat retouched tools and side- and end-scrapers are all represented (Figure 15, A-B), suggesting that tools made on this raw-materials were introduced into the area already flaked. Of particular relevance is the presence of two tang fragments from pressure-retouched arrowhead, one from a trihedral arrowhead. Both are typical of the Neolithic period in Oman (Charpentier 2004). One of them still conserves traces of adhesive substance on the proximal end (Figure 15, B). Finally, there is one end-scraper in quartz arenite with a particular V-shaped morphology. In conclusion, the assemblage is homogenous and seem to correspond to a single chronological period. Therefore, Area 17 represents a new and rare evidence of Neolithic occupation in the inner mountain fringe.

3.2.1.4. Area 22

Area 22 has been found on the south of the village of As Sayighi. Lithic materials are spread over a relatively vast area, of an extent of 230.000 m², comprising several contemporary (an electric tower), modern (a few fireplaces) and Islamic architectures (a cemetery) (Figure 16).

The material collected in Area 22 is rather heterogeneous. The main raw material present is the chert (73,8%), which includes different kinds pertinent to four macro-classes described. 5% of the total is represented by quartz arenite and almost 22% of the material is out of our classes. The low number of elements do not allow us to reconstruct the technical system, however we can describe some characteristic tools.

One borer is made on a quadrangular quartz arenite flake. Four end scrapers with a large front, obtained on laminar flakes and flakes are recorded. The typological assemblage is completed by lateral scrapers, generally straight and in some cases convex, and few bilateral pieces. We highlight the presence of a likely preformed narrow point (#47) and a probable bifacial tool, discarded during its preparation.

The three residual cores are very fragmentated, we can identify an unidirectional reduction system made on the

Figure 14. Aerial view of Area 17 and of the Ad Dakhiliyah region (above); the 20 x 2 m transect (below).

Figure 15. A-B) Two tangs from trihedral arrowheads in yellowish-beige chert. On the left is visible the presence of traces of adhesive substance on the proximal tip of the tang. C) A bifacial arrowhead on hyaline quartz (*the reconstruction of the arrowhead type/shape it is only hypothetical to help the reader visualize the tool approximate shape*).

Figure 16. Area 22. General view of the area of the lithic scatter and some of the collected materials on the surface.

straight débitage platform, which shows a lot of reflection accidents, leading to the discard of the core itself. One of the bladelets cores (#42) has a pyramidal shape created by a very narrow débitage surface, delimited by the bigger lateral extractions. Moreover, we underline the presence of the preparation of the straight platform, starting from the débitage surface. At last, we noted the use of the edge of blanks to draw blades and bladelets (#44) and two cases of bipolar on anvil technique (#5). The proximal part and the butt of blanks show the use of hard hammers with direct gesture and soft hammers with tangential motion, as it shows the presence of the lips.

In general, the assemblage is made of blades and bladelets, flakes and microflakes.

The first impression of the heterogenous assemblage seems confirmed, even though we can propose a prehistoric and protohistoric attribution.

3.2.2. Isolate Findings

Flaked materials have been occasionally found in different areas (Areas 3, 14, 20, 21), although not connected to any clear scatter or structure (Tab. 4). However, the presence of these materials suggests a human frequentation of the surveyed areas during the pre- or protohistoric periods. Most of them comes from areas around the Wadi Sahtan valley, and in particular west of the modern city of Rustaq.

Despite some of the collected materials seems homogenous with the Neolithic assemblages in the lithic scatters (Areas 11, 17, 22), we cannot exclude their attribution to later periods of the Omani Prehistory (Bronze or Iron Age). One particularly relevant finds is a end-scraper on quartz arenite that comes from Area 14, and that may fit with pre-Neolithic assemblages.

ID	POINTS	AREA	QUANTITY	RAW MATERIAL	TECHNOLOGY	TPOLOGY	CHRONOLOGICAL ATTRIBUTION
1	3004	Area 3	1	Chert	Convergent Flake	Bilateral point with alternate retouch	Indeterminate
2	3005	Area 3	1	Chert	Casson	Unretouched	Indeterminate
3	3006	Area 3	1	Chert	Proximal Fragment	Unretouched	Indeterminate
4	1007	Area 3	1	Quartz	Flake from bipolar on anvil	End Scraper	Indeterminate
5	1032	Area 14	1	Chert	Microflake	Unretouched	Pre-protohistoric
6	1032	Area 14	1	Chert	Cortical microflake	Unretouched	Pre-protohistoric
7	1032	Area 14	1	Quartz Arenite	Flake	Lateral end scraper	Palaeolithic?
8	2023	Area 14	1	Chert	Pebble	Unretouched	Pre-protohistoric
9	3030	Area 20	2	Chert	Microflake	Unretouched	Pre-protohistoric
10	3030	Area 20	1	Chert	Cortical flake	Unretouched	Pre-protohistoric
11	3030	Area 20	1	Chert	Bladelet	Lateral scraper	Pre-protohistoric
12	3030	Area 20	1	Chert	Quadrangular flake	Unretouched	Pre-protohistoric
13	1039	Area 20	1	Chert	Pyramidal semiturnal Core	Unretouched	Pre-protohistoric
14	2026	Area 20	1	Chert	Fragmented core	Unretouched	Pre-protohistoric
15	2026	Area 20	1	Chert	Flake	Unretouched	Pre-protohistoric
16	2027	Area 20	2	Chert	Flake	Unretouched	Pre-protohistoric
17	2027	Area 20	2	Chert	Quadrangular flake	Retouched	Pre-protohistoric
18	3031	Area 20	1	Chert	Flake	Unretouched	Pre-protohistoric
19	3033	Area 20	1	Chert	Blade	Scraper Notch	Pre-protohistoric
20	4019	Area 21	1	Chert	Laminar flake from bipolar on anvil	Unretouched	Pre-protohistoric

Table 4. List of Isolated finds.

Discussion

Preliminary results from survey are promising and has allowed to better define some pattern of prehistoric occupation in the Southern Batinah Region. The first aspect to remark is that the difference between the evidence recorded in the two areas, the coastal fringe and the foothill and mountainous zones. In the coastal areas prehistoric evidence is extremely difficult to be detected at least through surface surveying methodologies; vice

Figure 17. Above: main evidence in the foothill and mountains areas classified for typologies of finds. Below: preliminary model of Prehistoric Potential (PP) of the investigated region.

versa, new data has been gathered on the occupation of foothills and the mountainous areas of the Central Hajar Mountains. Main results are:

- In the eastern sector evidence of prehistoric frequentation are much scarcer (**Figures 17**), while the PP (Prehistoric Potential) of western areas is higher.
- Two new lithic scatter areas with Prehistoric materials have been identified (Areas 17 and 22), showing potential for future investigations;
- Area 11, partially investigated by D. Kennet and his collaborators has also provided new evidence that complete the available information on the Neolithic occupation of the area;
- The exploitation of varied raw-materials (different types of chert, hyaline quartz and quartz arenite) has been highlighted. An outcrop of radiolarite potentially exploited by prehistoric groups has been identified;
- We deepen the knowledge about the technical systems used by Neolithic groups. Several *chaîne opératoires* have been recognized, including bipolar on anvil that was not known in this region;
- New shell-middens have been identified on the costal zone; a chronological attribution to historic period has been proposed.

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